

SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF BANANA PSEUDOSTEM BORER, *ODOIPORUS LONGICOLLIS* OLIVIER INCIDENCE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH WEATHER PARAMETERS

Nikita S. Awasthi* and S. Sridharan

Department of Agricultural Entomology,
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore- 641 003, Tamil Nadu (India)nikita.agri19@gmail.com

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Abstract

Pseudostem borer of banana, Odoiporus longicollis (Olivier) is a serious monophagous pest occurring regularly in the majority of banana-growing states. The present study was conducted in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu to assess the seasonal dynamics of the population of adults of banana pseudostem borer and borehole damage on two banana cultivars namely Nendran and Karpooravalli. Peak incidence and borehole damage were maximum during October, 2014 and November, 2014 respectively, whereas the lower activity of adults and borehole damage was recorded from February to April, 2015. Incidence of adult and borehole damage was negatively and significantly correlated with maximum temperature, sunshine hours and evaporation, whereas morning relative humidity, evening relative humidity, and rainfall showed positive and significant correlation. The seasonal fluctuation of the adult population noted during 2014-2015 in residual pseudostem of cultivar Karpooravalli indicated the occurrence of adults and grubs was higher during October-2014 and September-2014, respectively. The weather factors influenced 82.90 and 96.50 percent on the occurrence of adults and grubs in residual pseudostem, respectively, which emphasizes the contribution of weather parameters on the incidence.

Keywords: *Pseudostem, monophagous, residual pseudostem, correlation*

Introduction

Among the pests of banana, pseudostem borer, *Odoiporus longicollis* (Olivier) is a serious monophagous pest that limits the production and productivity of banana. It has widespread occurrence in major banana-growing regions and is a nightmare for banana growers. Owing to its monophagous nature and voracious feeding habit it causes 10-90 percent yield loss depending on the infestation stage and management efficiency. Both the grubs and adults feed on banana pseudostem and cause extensive damage by tunneling, which results in the weakening of the stem. In severely infested plantations, more than 20 percent of plants do not flower (Padmanaban and Sathiamoorthy, 2001). Padmanaban and Kandasamy (2003) also reported the occurrence of banana pseudostem borer in residues of banana stem after harvest. The long life span of the adult weevil and the endophytic behaviour of the grub limits the efficacy of conventional management methods, especially chemical control using insecticides. For early detection and monitoring of this pest and the development of effective pest management programs, it is crucial to understand the seasonal incidence and its relation with weather parameters.

Materials And Method

In the objective to study seasonal dynamics of incidence of adult banana pseudostem borer and damage, observations were recorded at fortnight intervals, in two banana cultivars *viz.*, Nendran and Karpooravalli maintained at farmer's banana orchard, situated at Navavoor Pirivu, Coimbatore during 2014-2015. The number of adult weevils from outer leaf sheaths of 50 plants selected at random and the number of boreholes in each variety was noted. To assess the incidence on leftover pseudostem after harvest (residual pseudostem), monthly observations were taken by counting the number of adults and grubs from 20 freshly harvested leftover pseudostems selected at random in variety Karpooravalli.

The data for weather factors (independent variable) *viz.*, maximum and minimum temperature, morning and evening relative humidity, wind speed, sunshine hours, total rainfall and evaporation was obtained from Agro Climate Research Centre (ACRC), Coimbatore for the entire study period and their average standard fortnight and monthly average was worked out.

Statistical Analysis: To study the influence of different weather parameters on the incidence of banana pseudostem borer, mean of the observations were estimated and subjected to simple correlation matrices and multiple regression analyses using SPSS 16.0 statistical package.

Results And Discussion**Seasonal dynamics of banana pseudostem borer, *Odoiporus longicollis* Olivier**

The mean population of adults and mean number of boreholes recorded on the cultivars Nendran and Karpooravalli during the period of 1st August, 2014 to 30th July, 2015 in mentioned in Table 1. The data depicted in Table 1. revealed that, in both the cultivars there were fluctuations in the mean adult population per plant throughout the year. The peak population of adult *O. longicollis*, on Nendran was recorded during 10th October - 23rd October, 2014 with mean population of 11.92 adults per plant. Similarly, number of boreholes per plant was found maximum (15.74) during 7th November-20th November, 2014. Decline in population was observed during summer season, with a minimum adult population of 1.08 adults per plant during 7th March - 9th April, 2015. Boreholes per plant were found minimum during 13th February-26th February, 2015. Further build-up of population was observed during monsoon with more boreholes per plant. A similar trend was observed on Karpooravalli. The highest mean population of adults was observed during 10th October - 23rd October, 2014 (12.94 adults per plant) followed by 24th October - 6th November 2014 (10.82 adults per plant). The lowest mean number of adults per plant was recorded during 27th March -9th April, 2015 (2.46 adults per plant) followed by 13th March - 26th March, 2015 (3.08 adults per plant). The maximum number of boreholes observed was during 5th June-18th June, 2015 (12.68 boreholes per plants) followed by 7th November - 20th November, 2014 (12.12 boreholes per plants) and the minimum number of boreholes recorded were during 30th January -12th February, 2015 (4.36 boreholes per plant) followed by 13th February - 26th February 2015 (5.02 boreholes per plants).

After harvesting of the bunch, adults of *O. longicollis* are attracted towards the volatile released by cut stems and breed in those residual pseudostem. In an attempt to understand the incidence of pseudostem borer in residual pseudostem after harvest (Cv. Karpooravalli), the population of adults and grubs were recorded from twenty randomly selected residual pseudostems from August, 2014 to July, 2015 at monthly interval. The mean population of adults and grubs recorded from randomly selected residual pseudostems is presented in Fig. 1. The maximum number of adults was recorded during October-2014 (24.20 adults per pseudostem) followed by November-2014 and September with mean population of 21.65 and 17.75 adults per pseudostem, respectively. The population was the lowest during March, 2015 (5.20 adults per pseudostem) followed by April, 2015 (6.15 adults per

pseudostem). The population of grubs per pseudostem was the highest during September 2014 (8.25) followed by June, 2015 (7.65) and October, 2015 (7.15), whereas it was the lowest during April 2015 (3.75 grubs per pseudostem).

The present findings are in concurrence with the findings of Zhou and Wu (1986), who stated that, there were two population peaks of *O. longicollis*, in April-May and September - October. Devi *et al.* (2015). The results indicated that the pest breeds throughout the year, with slow activity during December to February. The highest damage (4.5 %) was observed during September 2010 and 4.6 % in 2011. Luo *et al.* (1985) stated that the density was high from late May to June and from late September to mid-October. Sudarshana Borah *et al.* (2020) found that in the Jorhat district of Assam, the percent infestation was peak during July to September and declined during November to January. The present study clearly indicates that the incidence of adults is followed by the presence of boreholes and the possibility of oviposition during this period. The pin head size boreholes which succeeds oviposition of pseudostem borer observed on the outer leaf sheath of pseudostem during October to January (Sridharan, 2014), further strengthen the present finding.

Relationship between the incidence of adult *Odoiporus longicollis* and weather parameters

Table 2. represents the association of weather factors with their impact on the incidence of adult weevil population in Nendran and Karpooravalli cultivars during 2014-2015. The incidence of the adult population on Nendran showed a significant inverse correlation with maximum temperature, sunshine hours, and evaporation ($r = -0.515, -0.491, \text{ and } -0.481$, respectively). Morning relative humidity, evening relative humidity, and rainfall impacted significantly positively ($r = 0.700, 0.789 \text{ and } 0.596$, respectively). The regression analysis also indicated a significant impact of weather factors on the occurrence of adult weevils up to 70 percent. A similar trend was observed in the cultivar Karpooravalli. The adult population of *O. longicollis* on Karpooravalli showed a highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature, sunshine hours and evaporation ($r = -0.415, -0.416 \text{ and } -0.388$ respectively), whereas morning relative humidity, evening relative humidity, and rainfall had significant positive correlation with adult population ($r = 0.646, 0.743 \text{ and } 0.600$ respectively). The regression analysis showed up to 61.70 percent influence of weather parameters on the incidence of pseudostem borer adults. The number of boreholes in Nendran also showed a highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature, sunshine hours, and evaporation ($r = -0.568, -0.611, \text{ and } -0.560$, respectively). On the other hand, morning relative humidity, evening relative humidity, and rainfall showed a significant positive influence on the boreholes of pseudostem borer ($r = 0.682, 0.751, \text{ and } 0.423$). All the weather factors together determine the variation in mean number of boreholes by 68.5 percent which was clear through regression analysis. Sunshine hours exerted a significant negative influence on the mean number of boreholes of pseudostem borer in Karpooravalli with a correlation coefficient of -0.509, whereas the influence of morning relative humidity and evening humidity was significantly positive ($r = 0.429 \text{ and } 0.602$). The results of regression analysis showed that all weather parameters together determine the variation in mean number of boreholes by 70.6 percent.

The influence of weather parameters on adults and grubs population in residual pseudostems of Karpooravalli during 2014-2015 was also studied (Table 2). The adult population showed a highly significant negative correlation with maximum temperature, sunshine hours and evaporation ($r = -0.680, -0.671 \text{ and } -0.624$). Morning relative humidity ($r = 0.679$) and evening relative humidity ($r = 0.714$) had a significant positive correlation with adult population. All the weather parameters together determined the variation in mean number of adults by 82.9

percent. The maximum temperature and sunshine hours showed a significant negative correlation with the population of grubs (r values -0.668 and -0.820), whereas, evening relative humidity exerted a significant positive influence ($r = 0.798$). All weather parameters together determine the variation in mean number of grubs by 96.5 percent.

The present result finds support by the work of Tayade *et al.* (2014), who reported that the population of *O. longicollis* was positively correlated with minimum temperature, morning relative humidity, evening relative humidity, average relative humidity, rainfall, and rainy days. Present results are in partial agreement with Devi *et al.* (2015), who reported a negative association of weevil damage with maximum temperature, minimum temperature, minimum relative humidity and rainfall akin to the present results reported but also a negative correlation with maximum relative humidity in contradiction to the present results. Present findings are contradictory to the findings of Indira Priyadarshini *et al.* (2015), Biswas *et al.* (2015) and Sudarshana Borah *et al.* (2020). The reason for contradictory results may be related to fact that the region/location taken for observation which might receive high average annual rainfall and experience maximum average temperature for weevil activity as compared to Coimbatore region (study area) with average low rainfall and temperature. Hence the differential results.

Conclusion

The adult population and number of boreholes were found maximum during the rainy season and minimum during the summer season. The influence of rainfall on relative humidity is positive which prevailed during September-October in Coimbatore can be attributed to the positive association of relative humidity with the occurrence of adult weevil and grubs in pseudostem. Likewise, during the rainy month September - October, the duration of sunshine hours would be low, which checks the escalation of temperature and hence, a negative association with the pest incidence. Similarly, the prevalence of more sunshine hours, high temperature, low rainfall, and low relative humidity during March - April with low incidence results in a positive association of temperature and sunshine hours and a negative association with relative humidity and rainfall. The present findings will help the farmers and plant protection personnel to monitor the incidence of pseudostem borer and early detection may help in effective and timely intervention. The present study throws light on the importance of field sanitation and proper disposal of residual pseudostem as the pest breeds in the residual pseudostems.

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Table. 1. Seasonal dynamics of banana pseudostem borer, *Odoiporus longicollis* Olivier in Nendran and Karpoorava

Fortnight	Nendran		Karpooravali		Temperature (°C)		Relative Humidity (%)		Rainfall (mm)	Wind speed (Kmph)	Sunshine hours	Evaporation (mm)
	Mean No. Adult per plant	Mean No. Boreholes per plant	Mean No. Adult per plant	Mean No. Boreholes per plant	Max.	Min.	RH (M)	RH (E)				
1 Aug-14 Aug 2014	4.42	8.44	3.84	7.94	31.6	23.2	81.6	57.1	3.8	6.9	9.5	5.6
15 Aug-28 Aug 2014	5.72	8.02	6.22	7.32	30.6	23.0	80.6	56.4	0.3	12.1	6.5	6.4
29 Aug-11 Sept 2014	5.94	9.42	6.36	7.62	32.6	22.4	86.4	52.1	5.2	7.1	7.9	6.2
12 Sept-25 Sept 2014	8.96	11.44	8.86	9.98	31.6	23.1	91.5	61.6	7.7	4.0	7.0	4.4
26 Sept-9 Oct 2014	8.82	11.3	9.38	9.86	29.7	22.4	92.9	71.6	11.8	4.5	4.3	3.6
10 Oct-23 Oct 2014	11.92	14.6	12.94	10.22	29.3	21.8	93.6	65.1	6.7	2.9	4.5	3.0
24 Oct- 6 Nov 2014	9.76	13.24	10.82	11.68	30.4	21.6	90.2	58.3	0.2	5.2	5.8	4.0
7 Nov-20 Nov,2014	8.26	15.74	8.36	12.12	28.4	20.6	86.9	54.9	0.1	4.4	2.8	3.4
21 Nov-4 Dec 2014	6.86	12.34	7.82	11.52	29.2	21.5	89.6	61.5	0.8	5.3	4.7	3.7
5 Dec-18 Dec 2014	8.04	10.52	7.88	9.4	28.6	20.9	79.0	50.9	0.4	4.7	3.9	2.9
19 Dec 2014-1 Jan 2015	7.54	11.46	6.54	8.88	30.3	18.7	87.9	45.3	0.0	4.3	8.1	4.1
2 Jan-15 Jan 2015	6.24	9.72	5.44	5.36	30.0	19.2	83.6	49.1	0.0	5.4	7.1	4.5
16 Jan-29 Jan 2015	3.72	6.66	4.24	5.08	30.6	20.0	83.2	41.5	0.0	6.3	7.7	5.3
30 Jan-12 Feb 2015	3.12	6.28	4.98	4.36	33.2	19.3	77.4	28.4	0.0	5.6	9.9	6.0
13 Feb-26 Feb 2015	2.72	3.22	4.24	5.02	33.2	19.3	77.4	28.4	0.0	5.6	9.9	6.0
27 Feb-12 Mar 2015	2.78	5.26	3.84	5.68	34.9	22.9	78.1	31.7	0.0	6.0	9.1	6.6
13 Mar-26 Mar 2015	1.98	4.46	3.08	6.68	35.6	25.2	80.2	36.9	0.0	5.7	7.7	6.8
27 Mar-9 April 2015	1.08	7.56	2.46	6.12	33.5	23.6	85.5	49.6	3.3	5.0	6.2	5.7
9 April- 23 April	3.46	5.94	4.12	5.44	34.2	23.4	85.9	51.8	4.1	4.5	8.1	6.0
24 April-7 May 2015	6.48	8.96	7.34	8.48	31.3	23.3	92.9	68.0	10.1	3.7	4.1	3.9
8 May-21 May 2015	8.02	10.5	7.22	9.48	33.3	23.6	90.0	57.1	1.0	4.8	6.8	5.1
22 May- 4 June 2015	6.48	8.96	8.34	10.66	33.4	23.7	81.2	47.9	0.2	7.9	6.5	6.6
5 June-18 June 2015	6.82	9.02	7.86	12.68	31.0	23.7	80.4	60.1	3.2	12.3	6.1	6.1
19 June-2 July 2015	7.08	9.56	9.66	11.98	32.6	22.9	85.9	47.6	0.0	8.0	7.7	6.9
3 July-16 July 2015	8.26	10.74	7.38	10.52	31.6	22.9	84.8	53.0	0.4	9.7	5.7	6.4
17 July- 30 July 2015	8.04	10.52	8.98	11.74	32.2	23.4	82.6	50.7	0.1	9.5	7.3	7.0

Table. 2. Correlation between banana pseudostem borer, *Odoiporus longicollis* Olivier and weather parameters

Weather parameter	Adults in Nendran	Boreholes in Nendran	Adults in Karpooravalli	Boreholes in Karpooravalli	Adults in Karpooravalli residual pseudostem	Grubs in Karpooravalli residual pseudostem
Temperature Max. (°C)	-0.515**	-0.568**	-0.415*	-0.253 ^{NS}	-0.680*	-0.668*
Temperature Min. (°C)	0.024 ^{NS}	0.033 ^{NS}	0.096 ^{NS}	0.332 ^{NS}	-0.076 ^{NS}	0.137 ^{NS}
RH (M) (%)	0.700**	0.682**	0.646**	0.429*	0.679*	0.350 ^{NS}
RH (E) (%)	0.789**	0.751**	0.743**	0.602**	0.714**	0.798**
Rainfall (mm)	0.596**	0.423*	0.600**	0.268 ^{NS}	0.496 ^{NS}	0.427 ^{NS}
Wind speed (Kmph)	-0.112 ^{NS}	-0.148 ^{NS}	-0.062 ^{NS}	0.127 ^{NS}	-0.220 ^{NS}	0.062 ^{NS}
Sunshine hours	-0.491*	-0.611**	-0.416*	-0.509**	-0.671*	-0.820**
Evaporation (mm)	-0.481*	-0.560**	-0.388*	-0.185 ^{NS}	-0.624*	-0.550 ^{NS}

*Significant at 5%, **Significant at 1%, ^{NS} – Non significant

Fig. 1. Seasonal dynamics of banana pseudostem borer, *Odoiporus longicollis* Olivier in Karpooravalli residual pseudostem

